

Synthetic Oxygen Carriers : Properties of some Cobalt(II) Schiff Base Chelates

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This paper gives a brief review of the research done in our laboratory on the oxygen carrier properties of some cobalt(II) Schiff base chelates. Initially monomeric molecular oxygen adducts were isolated and characterized. The esr spectra of these adducts suggested that they could be formulated as Co(III)-O_2^- species, and that Co-O-O has a bent structure. Recent studies show that the reversible oxygen uptake ability of these cobalt(II) chelates correlate their ease of oxidation to cobalt(III), as measured by cyclic voltammetry.

COBALT(II) Schiff base complexes have long been known to reversibly bind molecular oxygen.¹ Following the discovery by Tsumaki² that crystals of N, N'-ethylenebis (salicylideneiminato) cobalt(III) darken when exposed to air and return to their original color when placed in a vacuum, Calvin and coworkers³ conducted an exhaustive study of the oxygen carrying properties of this compound and some of its derivatives in the solid state. They discovered that reversible oxygen uptake was possible only with an "active" crystalline form of the complex. There has been a continuing interest in the possible application of such compounds in self-supporting oxygen systems¹ of various types. Also there is some interest in the use of such cobalt chelates as catalysts for the air oxidation of different substrates.⁴ However, the most significant recent achievement is that reported by Hoffman and Petering⁵ who reconstituted globin with cobalt(II) protoporphyrin IX, the analogue of heme, and found that the resulting coboglobin has oxygen carrier properties similar to hemoglobin.

The structure and symbols of the cobalt chelates used in our investigations are represented in Fig. 1

Initial studies on the reaction of oxygen with Co (acacen) in solution at room temperature resulted in a non-stoichiometric gas uptake by these solutions, which persisted slowing over a period of days. However, at temperatures below 0° toluene solutions of Co(acacen) containing pyridine or substituted pyridine reacted reversibly with molecular oxygen in a well-defined manner.⁶ It was possible to isolate solid dioxygen adducts from these solutions which were monomeric species of the type Co(acacen) BO_2 , where B is a unidentate ligand in the axial position. Floriani and Calderazzo⁷ have also isolated such an adduct, but prior to this work the only species reported⁸ were the bridged dimers of the type $\text{L}_5\text{Co-O}_2\text{-CoL}_5$.

The bridged dimers are diamagnetic low-spin d^6 cobalt(III) complexes with a peroxide bridge, formulated as $\text{Co(III)-O}_2^{2-}\text{-Co(III)}$. In contrast to this the monomeric adducts, Co-O_2 , are paramagnetic with a static magnetic susceptibility of approximately 1.9BM, which corresponds to one unpaired electron. Furthermore, the monomeric species has a very strong ir band at about 1130 cm^{-1} which disappears and reappears upon the removal and addition of oxygen, respectively. This absorption band is assigned to the O-O stretching frequency of the adduct Co-O-O. This value of 1130 cm^{-1} corresponds closely with 1145 cm^{-1} for O_2^- but not with 836 cm^{-1} for O_2^{2-} .⁹ These results suggest that the 1:1 adducts can be formulated as Co(III)-O_2^- , where one has essentially a low-spin d^6 cobalt(III) and a coordinated superoxide ion.

R' = CH ₃	R = H	Co (acacen)	
"	R = C ₆ H ₅	Co (Phacacen)	
"	R = CH ₃	Co (meacacen)	
R' = C ₆ H ₅	R = H	Co (benacen)	
R' = CH ₃	O = S	R = H	Co (sacsacen)

Fig. 1.

That this formulation is justified, is supported by the esr spectra of these monomeric oxygen adducts.¹⁰ The spectra have eight lines of equal intensity, characteristic of interaction of the unpaired spin with a single ⁵⁹Co nucleus. The evaluation of the esr spectra by standard methods,¹¹ indicates approximately 90% transfer of spin density from cobalt upon oxygen adduct formation. This means that the representation Co(III)-O₂⁻ provides the best indication of the charge separation in these systems. On the basis of the ir spectra⁶ and the esr spectra¹⁰ of these adducts, it was also possible to speculate that they may have a bent Co-O-O structure. This structure has now been established by means of single crystal x-ray studies¹² for the adduct Co (benacen)-(py)O₂ (Fig. 2.)

Fig. 2.

On the basis that the cobalt-oxygen adduct can be represented as Co(III)-O₂⁻, it follows that the reaction of these complexes with oxygen can best be described as an electron transfer from cobalt(II) to the oxygen molecule. This suggests¹ that the reversible oxygen uptake ability of these complexes should be closely related to their redox potentials. This has recently been established¹³ by the results in our laboratory which show that there is a linear correlation between the equilibrium constants for oxygen adduct formation and the ease of oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) of the substrates.

Spectral changes were recorded for solutions of cobalt chelates containing different bases at different partial pressures of oxygen and at different temperatures in order to estimate thermodynamic data for oxygen uptake (eq. 1).

Upon contact with oxygen, toluene solutions of Co(L)B underwent spectral changes as a function of oxygen pressure. The spectral changes were immediate upon shaking the solution with oxygen, and the complex, Co(L)B.O₂, was stable, as judged by the constancy of the spectra after equilibrium was reached. The total change was reversible, and the original

spectrum was restored upon evacuating the system to remove oxygen.

The equilibrium constants were obtained using the Hill relation.

$$Y/(1-Y) = \frac{\text{Co(L)B.O}_2}{\text{Co(L)B}} = K\text{O}_2^n \quad (2)$$

The slope of the line, experimentally determined from a plot of $\log \frac{Y}{1-Y}$ vs. $\log \text{Po}_2$, ranged from 0.9 to 1.1 but was constrained in all cases to $n=1.0$, and the value of $\log K\text{O}_2$ was obtained from the intercept of the best straight line of slope 1.0. Values of $Y/(1-Y)$ between 0.25 and 4.0 only were used where possible in determining $K\text{O}_2$. The equilibrium constants of the compounds studied and the conditions under which these were collected are given in Tables I and II.

Redox potentials were determined by cyclic voltammetry. The potential changes for the anodic and cathodic sweeps of the cobalt(II-III) couple were reversible.¹⁴ The potentials of the Co(L) couples were determined in neat pyridine. The reaction at the electrode surface corresponds to

since the potentials obtained for Co(L) were the same whether starting with Co^{II}(acacen) or Co^{III}(acacen)-py₂⁺;¹⁵ or with Co^{II}(benacen) or Co^{III}(benacen)py₂⁺. The potentials obtained for Co(II) → Co(III) oxidations are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF OXYGEN UPTAKE (LOG K_{O₂}) TO POLAROGRAPHIC HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS (E_{1/2}) FOR CO (BENACEN) B COMPLEXES

Base, B	pK _a ^a	^b log K _{O₂} , mm ⁻¹	^{c,d} E _{1/2} , volts
<i>n</i> -BuNH ₂	10.61 ^e	-0.75	-0.74
<i>iso</i> -BuNH ₂	10.49 ^e	-0.74	-0.73
N-MeIm	7.25	-0.82	-0.72
5-Cl-N-MeIm	5.45	-0.99	-0.67
<i>sec</i> -BuNH ₂	10.56	-1.18	-0.62
3, 4 lutidine	6.47	-1.66	-0.56
py	5.27	-2.03	-0.50
CN-py	1.86	-2.68	-0.35

(a) From K. Schofield, "Hetero-Aromatic Nitrogen Compounds," Plenum Press, New York, N.Y., 1967, p. 146, except as indicated.

- (b) Measurements were made in $10^{-3}M$ base in toluene solution at -21° . Standard State of 1 torr
- (c) The solution was $-10^{-3}M$ in complex and 0.1M in $(C_2H_5)_4NClO_4$, $E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \pm 0.01$ volts vs. SCE. Potential is for anodic wave, $Co(II) \rightarrow Co(III)$, at the hanging drop mercury electrode. $T=23^\circ$.
- (d) Acetonitrile solutions containing 4% base, B, by volume.
- (e) "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics," 42nd ed., 1960-61, p. 1749.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF OXYGEN UPTAKE (LOG K_{O_2}) TO POLAROGRAPHIC HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$) FOR $Co(L)py$ COMPLEXES

Compound	^a log K_{O_2} , mm^{-1}	^b $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, volts
Co(<i>r</i> -cacen)py	-0.28	-0.59
Co(Phacacen)py	-0.89	-0.55
Co(Meacacen)py	-1.12	-0.54
Co(benacen)py	-1.36	-0.50
Co(sacacen)py	-2.12	-0.33
Co(<i>p</i> -MeOTPP)py ^c	-3.1	-0.23

- (a) Standard state of 1 torr. - Measurements were made in 1.6% pyridine-toluene at -31° .
- (b) Measurements were made in neat pyridine at 23° . The solution was $10^{-3}M$ in complex and 0.1M in $(C_2H_5)_4NClO_4$. $E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \pm 0.01$ volts vs. S. C. E. Potential is for anodic wave, $Co(II) \rightarrow Co(III)$, at the hanging drop mercury electrode.
- (c) *p*-MeOTPP = α , β , γ , δ -tetra(*p*-methoxyphenyl)porphyrin. See reference 16.

Most of the previous investigations^{6,16,17} of the reversible oxygen uptake reactions of $Co(L)B$ have been concerned with the effect of the axial base B. The bonding properties of the bases, B, used in these investigations change substantially from pure σ bonding (saturated amines) to the σ and π bonding properties of substituted pyridines and substituted imidazoles.

Generally the pK_a of the conjugate acid is taken as a measure of the σ bond strength of the amine. The observed trends (Table I) in oxygen carrying ability of $Co(benacen)B$ for analogous bases are seen to crudely parallel the pK_a order, thus n -BuNH₂ > *iso*-BuNH₂; N-MeIm > 5-Cl-N-MeIm; 3, 4 lutidine > py > CN-py.

The butylamines were studied in order to establish the importance of steric factors. The bases, *t*-BuNH₂, *sec*-BuNH₂, *iso*-BuNH₂, and *n*-BuNH₂ have similar pK_a 's and these saturated bases can only σ bond, thus any change in the oxygenation ability of $Co(benacen)B$ is expected to result from steric interac-

tions of the base. Experiments show that with *t*-BuNH₂ the complex is only weakly sensitive to oxygen, but it does slowly undergo an irreversible oxidation. The base, *sec*-BuNH₂, is less sterically hindered, but still the steric effects are significant enough to alter the oxygen uptake of $Co(benacen)B$ from that expected when compared with *n*-BuNH₂. For *iso*-BuNH₂, little steric effects are noted indicating that the methyl group β to NH₂ has only a minor detrimental influence on the oxygen uptake ability of $Co(benacen)$.

The other important factor to consider is π bonding. The theoretical model predicts that the strength of the cobalt-oxygen bond is partly dependent on the extent of back donation of the $3d_{xz}$ (or $3d_{yz}$) electrons from the cobalt atom into the half-filled π^* orbital of the oxygen. Bases coordinated *trans* to oxygen will be in direct competition with the oxygen molecule for the 3 $d\pi$ electrons of the cobalt atom. Thus, according to the theory, a good π donating base forces more electron density on the cobalt and enhances the π bonding electron flow from cobalt to oxygen. Furthermore, because of the symmetry of the orbitals involved, the axial ligand can effectively donate its electrons to the d_{xz} (or d_{yz}) orbitals of cobalt which are the orbitals that π bond to oxygen. It follows that imidazoles, which are better π donors¹⁸ than pyridine, have the greater enhancement on the oxygen carrier ability of $Co(benacen)$ (Table I). However, the effectiveness of the π donating ability of an axial ligand can be superseded by a strong σ donor, e.g. *n*-BuNH₂.

A linear correlation (Fig. 3) exists between the halfwave potential of $Co(II \rightarrow III)$ and the ability of the $Co(benacen)B$ species to react with oxygen. It is interesting to note that on the basis of redox potentials, the π donating bases show the same correlation observed for σ bases. In addition, steric effects cause no problem in the correlation. It would appear that the halfwave potential gives a measure of the electron density on the cobalt as a composite of σ , π , and steric phenomena. Thus, the principle function of the base is to "activate" the cobalt complex by making it a better reducing agent.

The effect of changes in the equatorial ligands on the oxygen uptake of $Co(L)py$ complexes is shown by the data in Table II. Thus, a phenyl group on the carbonyl carbon, (*benacen*), proves to be a better withdrawer of electron density from cobalt than a phenyl on the methylene carbon (*Phacacen*). The methyl group in the 3 position also decreases the

Fig. 3

ability of reversible oxygenation. This was not expected because the methyl group should contribute electron density to the system and enhance its oxygen affinity. The result is not understood, but it is in accord with the small change in redox potential.

Two other factors are important in ascertaining changes in the equatorial ligands, (1) the nature of the bonding atoms, i.e. electronegativity and π electron withdrawal properties, and (2) the π delocalization of the metal's electron density over the equatorial ligand. A decrease in electronegativity of the ligand atoms should facilitate the oxygen carrier ability of the complex, whereas π electron withdrawal from the cobalt should have the opposite effect. In this con-

text, it is important to note that the replacement of O in (acacen) by S in (sacsacen) results in a weaker Co-O₂ bond. Koehler and Cummings¹⁹ suggest that the sulfur ligand facilitates electron withdrawal from cobalt by in-plane d-d π back-bonding between cobalt and sulfur. This lowering of electron density on cobalt, results in the complex being a less effective oxygen carrier.

The porphyrin ligand is thought to delocalize more electron density from cobalt into the ligand π system, accounting for the lower oxygen uptake ability of cobalt porphyrin Co(p-MeOTPP)py compared to the cobalt Schiff base chelates (Table II).

Fig. 4.

Regardless of the mechanism of electron withdrawal from cobalt, the halfwave potentials give a relative measure of the electron density on cobalt. The oxygen uptake ability correlates linearly (Fig. 4) with the halfwave potential. This correlation holds in spite of changes such as the framework of the (aca π) ligand, the donor atoms (O, S, and N), and the π delocalization properties of the quadridentate chelate group (Schiff bases, porphyrins and macrocycles). The results support the hypothesis that the oxygen carrying ability of metal complexes depend on their ease of oxidation.

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